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A SOCIOLOGICAL BASE OF THE IMAGINATIVE SYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL ADS

Svitlana Pryshchenko <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-3482-6858>¹**Expanded Abstract:**

Purpose: Commercial ads in the interdisciplinary study are considered as a product of culture in the context of actual trends of advertising design development – a specific kind of creative activity, and the contemporary design process is presented as a synthesis of sociocultural, graphic and marketing aspects in postmodern period.

Methodology: The author substantiates and discloses necessary scientific methods: sociocultural, axiological, and art-aesthetics. **Results and Conclusions:** The issues of advertising ideas visualization have been identified, and the arsenal of visual tools in combination with computer technologies is structured. Mass specifics of Advertising are proved. A simple illustrative accompaniment of commercial information has been replaced by the emergence of new styles in the 19th–20th century, the using of creative advertising technologies and polystylism at the beginning of 21st century, and the intensification of branding and rebranding processes. The form, essence and specificity of advertising image, its symbolic significance and importance as a means of visual communication are revealed, and scientifically substantiated definition of the imaginative system of advertising graphics is proposed.

Practical implications: In the framework of a specific visual-verbal model, the advertisement should have a clear communicative structure, sociocultural aspects, visual semantics, emotionality, conciseness, contrast and dynamic colour balance, originality, clarity of the image, art-aesthetics level, and stimulate the intellectual and emotional activity of consumers.

Value: This research is important at the theoretical, practical and educational levels and will promote the development of advertising in Eastern Europe, and in particular in Ukraine. Some of the allegations require further research in the fields of visual arts, visual culture and visual communications in order to implement contemporary design concepts taking into account the cultural tectonics of regions.

Keywords: commercial ads, media, stylistics, visual image, communication, mass culture

SOCIOLOŠKO OZADJE DOMISELNEGA SISTEMA KOMERCIALNIH OGLASOV

Razširjen povzetek:

Namen: Komercialni oglasi so v interdisciplinarni študiji obravnavani kot produkt kulture v okviru aktualnih trendov razvoja oglaševalskega oblikovanja, kot posebna vrsta ustvarjalne dejavnosti, sodobni oblikovalski proces pa je predstavljen kot sinteza sociokulturnih, grafičnih in marketinških vidikov v postmodernem obdobju.

Metodologija: Avtorica članka razkriva in utemeljuje potrebne znanstvene metode: sociokulturne, aksiološke in likovno-estetske.

Rezultati in zaključki: Opredeljena je problematika vizualizacije oglaševalskih idej, predstavljena so vizualna orodja v kombinaciji z računalniškimi tehnologijami, ki se uporabljajo za ustvarjanje oglasov. Dokazane so posebnosti množičnega oglaševanja. Ilustrativni dodatek k komercialnim sporočilom je nadomestil razvoj novih stilov 19.–20. stoletja, uporaba kreativnih oglaševalskih tehnologij in polistilizma na začetku 21. stoletja ter intenziviranje procesov blagovne znamke in preimenovanja le-te. Predstavljeni so oblika, bistvo in specifičnost oglaševalskih podob, njihov simbolni pomen in pomembnost kot orodje vizualne komunikacije, predlagana je znanstveno utemeljena opredelitev domiselnega sistema oglaševalske grafike.

Praktične implikacije: V okviru določenega vizualno-besednega modela mora imeti oglas naslednje specifikke: jasno komunikacijsko strukturo, sociokulturne vidike, vizualno semantiko, čustvenost, jedratost, kontrast in dinamično barvno ravnovesje, izvirnost, jasnost, likovno-estetsko raven, spodbuditi mora intelektualno in čustveno aktivnost in vpetost potrošnikov.

Vrednost: Ta raziskava je pomembna na teoretični, praktični in izobraževalni ravni in bo spodbujala razvoj oglaševanja v Vzhodni Evropi, zlasti v Ukrajini. Nekatere trditve kličejo po nadaljnjih raziskavah na področju vizualnih umetnosti, vizualne kulture in vizualnih komunikacij za implementacijo sodobnih oblikovalskih konceptov ob upoštevanju kulturne tektonike regij.

Ključne besede: komercialni oglasi, mediji, stilistika, vizualna podoba, komunikacija, množična kultura.

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Introduction

Nowadays, a visual approach is clearly defined, which tends to be concise and should provide a quick and unambiguous perception of information. Expansion of the global communicative space, rapid development of technologies, difficult socio-economic conditions, contradictory intercultural and ethno-cultural tendencies increase the attention to effective means of visualization of advertising ideas. In our opinion, the basic components of the professionalism of advertising designers are graphic design training, understanding of sociocultural context, and marketing. In spite of its main commercial function (Bovee & Arens 1995), advertising was recognized as cultural phenomenon due to visual aids of advertising communication that become logical reflection of sociocultural state of society in definite periods.

Research of cultural-aesthetics component in advertising has the aim to systematize visual means of information and make a complex definition of their functional and visual specifics in communication area of modern society, which is much wider than ten years ago. At the beginning of the 21st century great changes happened in conception of design and advertising because of the processes of globalization and simultaneous ethno-cultural identification, hyper consumerism and parallel lowering of general cultural level of society. James Lull, an American social scientist known for research on the interaction between communications technology and culture, figuring out how media technology is becoming an integral part of our daily lives, says that mass culture should be seen as a very important factor (Lull 2002). William Mitchel had focused on media theory and visual culture. He claimed that broad interest in language and textuality had given way to a new interest in the notion of visuality. Since language could not offer a full explanation of reality, cultural theorists were united in their increasing emphasis on the power of the visual in art, science, and indeed, everyday life where media and communication rank as determinants (Mitchel, 1995). Larisa Fedotova considers advertising in terms of mass culture. With the help of advertising communications, works of art, both past and present, become available to all categories of the population (Fedotova, 2002).

The purpose and objective of the research

Unfortunately, in most cases modern means of ad information do not contribute to forming outlook, art thinking development, aesthetic perception of reality etc. Visual aids are not end in itself: form, space and visual interrelation become means of visualization of ideas. On the base of the analysis of modern adverts we can clearly separate two main tendencies of visualization: first – ideological orientation of middle class consumers to “life in luxury style”, second – orientation towards mass consumer, catching attention, exclusive brightness and diversity of colours in advertisements. Consumerism became an ideology of postmodernism; mass media popularize hedonistic way of life and consuming type of personality (Pryshchenko, 2018). **The objective of our research is to analyze a sociological base of the imaginative system in commercial ads.**

Referring to the works of Ukrainian-Polish scientist Roman Sapen`ko, who considers communicative, semiotic and cultural-aesthetics aspects of advertising and defines that the bar and core of ad appeal is axiological complex, with the help of which advertising can touch individual values and aspirations of consumers. This complex becomes a basis for other elements of ads world (Sapen`ko, 2005). It is necessary to add that modern advertising forms trends of definite style of life, social behaviour, principles of use and moral norms. Now, ideals, values, cultural samples, heroes of different epochs and cultures: heritage, borrowing, reproductive.

Research methods

State of the problem indicates lack of scientific research on the artistic aspects of advertising. The humanities and art scientists do not disclose the influence of art on ad graphics and formation of its stylistics. Isolated scientific works have described character and do not give the idea of the advisability of developing advertising. That is why, in the process of complex research of commercial ads we used the following methodological attitudes: sociocultural, axiological, and art-aesthetics. Sociocultural method determines the advertising as part of mass culture (Moles, 1973; Eco, 1996; Featherstone 2007; Shtompka, 2007); axiological – advertising graphics should be considered as derivative product due to a set of values and norms of the particular historical period (Barthes 2003; Borghini 2010; Mass Communications and the Advertising Industry 1984); and art aesthetics – gives understanding the influence of art styles on advertising and identify contemporary stylistic trends (Heller 2000; McRobbie 1994; Shulykov 2011).

Research results

Visual aids of advertising changed greatly – modern appearance of advertising appeals differs much from advertising of 19th century by graphic means and methods of psychological influence on consumer. Generalization and classification of practical materials of ad appeals in 18th–21st centuries allows coming to conclusion that advertising, and after it, design borrows style features of graphic and arts

and crafts world art. Advertising evolved from illustrative accompanying of commercial information to the appearance of new styles (or pseudo-styles) in frames of mass culture of second part of 20th – the beginning of 21st century. In this context a lot of mistakes in advertising graphics were exposed: prevalence of stereotypes, primitivism, vulgarity and the absence of national image of major countries; pop-art, kitsch (arrogance), eclectics leading in ads. In spite of main task of advertising – attracting attention of potential clients to one of many products, as a rule similar products, and create its positive image for long term memorizing, means of visualization mostly have low aesthetic level. Considerable commercialisation went through, though, influenced the state and character of mass culture. As a result of huge economic and State building difficulties at the end of '80s–'90s of the last century Ukraine lost control over the production of own mass cultural product and its spread, giving it to foreign, especially to American and Russian producers.

Also, it is necessary to remind the reader of a little known fact that one of the most well-known art critics Vyacheslav Glazychev considered decadence of mass culture in his work "Problems of mass culture". Analysing tendencies of occidental conceptions of mass culture he underlined ideologism of their constructions, which have clear and straight orientation to consumerism, definite universal values of "members of united club of consumers": comprehensiveness of mass culture gives its characteristics absolute dominant, forcing out and suppressing elite-cultural ideal of creative personality, changing it into ideal homo-consumers (Glazychev, 1970).

Famous sociologist Arman Deyan considered that the basic function of advertising is that it converts product into drug analogue, as it injects stupefy due to which purchasing of the product immediately gives the feeling of facilitation to consumer, bordering to euphoria, and enslaves him for a long time. If ad announcement is optimal by sense and form, it should raise as delight as anxiety simultaneously, create anguish presentiment pleasure and desire to get it in any way (Deyan, 1993).

Researcher Anelia Petrova also considers the problem of prestige in behaviour of consumer as a support of identification of personality in social hierarchy (Petrova, 2010). A fashion becomes social norm of consumption. Orientation of a person to a group of luxury products is given as wish to make the quality of life better. Purposefully, "global" consumer with universal standards is formed in modern society.

The main problem of advertising creativity is finding balance between commerce and aesthetics. Advertising philosophy is directed to getting profits, which is understood as the most important part of advertising process. But culturological, outlook and moral-psychological parts are also of great importance. Especially the above mentioned parts of ad process makes a base of "platform" of visualization ad idea. Orientation of production to regional groups of consumers, significant change of market policy presupposed cardinal change in tasks and character of advertising: socio-psychological, cultural and aesthetical indices become very actual. Definition of imagery as specific means of creating image from the point of view of definite aesthetic ideal is a key to understanding the process of projecting mythological image in advertising design. Many consumers need not advertised goods but their images, symbols of prestige, possibility as means to follow definite style of life. Model of behaviour due to social fashion and outcome style of life is a reflection of definite outlook, system of values, hierarchy of inner aims formed in their mind.

Little researched topic remains visual-verbal code of advertising communications. Advertising becomes a sign that sells not a product itself but its symbolic reflection. Jean Bodriar criticized modern society that it becomes a society of consumerism where everything is materialized in signs and goods. He separated two types of consumerism: first satisfies the needs of a person, another is a sign of consumerism that become as specific code, language of social conversation demonstrative and long-lasting. From information, advertising has moved to suggestion, then to "invisible suggestion", now its purpose is to control consumption; sociologists have repeatedly expressed the fear that this threatens with totalitarian enslavement of man and his needs. Bodriar thinks that arrogance has its own base as a type of mass culture: art forms are not created now, they only vary and are repeated. Weakness in creating new forms is a symptom of art ruin. Philosopher comes to the conclusion that modern art is in the state of standstill: already known forms are varied and their combinations are long lasting. Purchasing products or services person reacts not on their differences but on their sign essence differences (Bodriar 2020).

As alternative to globalization processes with their aspiration to standardization and assimilation of cultural peculiarities; processes of self-identification of nations are actualized in design and advertising. One of the directions of design research is examining the influence of ethno-art and, especially colouristic traditions on modern project culture. Balance of national and international in design activity and advertising communications are actual and not homogeneous. Target audience research from the point of view of mentality has very big prognosis force in advertising, because psycho-emotion peculiarities are already stable indices and widespread to great amount of population. Every country has its own cultural traditions, lack of respect ruins the strategy of a firm.

During 20th century definitions of international sense of design dominated in society, so the most interesting design form-creating inventions in the era of industrial production were international. But now, when manufacturers orient on small output products, it becomes possible to demarcate the national stylistics. Unfortunately, design objects at the end of 20th century – beginning of 21st century contained mechanistic borrowings of rural art motives and putting them out on national objects of printed and outdoor advertising, packing, souvenirs.

A negative phenomenon of pseudo-nationalization was formed and consolidated at that time (e.g. pseudo-Ukrainian, pseudo-Russian, pseudo-Japanese, pseudo-Orient styles). Though, the use of ethno-motives in ads should not be the «decoration» of advertising

products, but it should be looking for new national forms of ad, saving regional cultural values in modern life, because accelerated speed of globalization brings world to obliteration of borders.

In conditions of sociocultural dynamics, we can observe “washing out” of stylistic trends or even their absence that is generally defined by term “postmodernism” as presence of typical eclectics in post-industrial society and variety of artistic research in the second part of 20th century. From the point of view of Jean Leotard postmodernism is not new epoch, but modernism in the stage of the next renovation (Leotard, 1998). It should be pointed out that borders of art and arrogance are washed out now more than in any other time, so the most problematic question is on stylistic features, art-aesthetics parameters, criteria of modern art and advertising products assessment. Postmodernism has its own typological features: the use of any ready forms from art to utility, widespread of photography and computer special effects, deliberate violation of commensurable quantities of visual elements, borrowing the ideas from other types of art, remake, interpretation, combination, fragmentation, epatage, installation, collageness and circulation (Postmodernism, 1994). Now the frames of postmodernism are widening; forming of new stylistic trends in architecture, art, design and advertising is made by deliberate synthetic approach in the use of variable elements, wide spread of irony and giving new context to old forms, complexity of the sense of harmony, increasing the variety of genres, reinterpretation of art traditions, accepting the coexistence of different cultures and dialogue of cultures (Pryshchenko, 2018).

The following figures (Figure 1–Figure 5) demonstrate the postmodern stylistics in the commercial ads produced during the second half of 20th and early 21st century.

Figure 1: James Rosenquist. Tide washing powder, 1975 (<https://www.pinterest.com>)

Figure 2: Change the colour range. Fire of Cointreau, 1999 (<https://www.pinterest.com>)

Figure 3: Lego ads, 2012 (<https://www.pinterest.com>)

Figure 4: Porsche ads, 1967 (<https://www.pinterest.com>)

Figure 5: Faber Castells colour pencil ads, 2010 (<https://www.pinterest.com>)

Discussion

The imaginative system in commercial ads is presented as a visual-verbal model, in which advertising appeal should have clear communicative structure, visual semantics, archetypal, contrast and dynamic balance of colours, easily understood images, should be aesthetically pleasing and stimulate the emotional activity of consumers. Creation of ads is a complex process in the fields of art-project activity, industry, consumption, and marketing. The principles of visualization as synthesis of colour harmony, aesthetics, artistic imagery, originality of the picture are formulated.

Advertising products of the epoch of postmodernism are created with the use of stylistic principles of postmodernism. But, modern consumer is very difficult to attract, so it is necessary to use creative approaches, to aspire to give additional aesthetic pleasure to consumers, compel to them to definite «decoding» of advertising appeal. From the point of view of famous Bulgarian advertiser Christo Kaftandgiev's sense of postmodernist approaches – which are used also in the theory of communications, and in that there is no good and bad communications, sign systems, codes and others – their value is defined exclusively by concrete communicative situation (Kaftandgiev, 2005).

A special role is played by the creation of the image – the ideal image of the company, personality, and subject. Many consumers do not need advertised goods, but their images, symbols of prestige, the ability to thus imitate the lifestyle of idols. Thus, aesthetic perception gives the opportunity to the average person through the advertising image to feel satisfaction, self-confidence, involvement in the beauty of everyday life. The stylistic diversity of beginning the 21st century determined by world cultural processes, demonstrates the diversity in the choice of means of artistic expression – from remakes of paintings and descriptions to solely font posters, from artistic experiments with photographs to the latest 3D photography simulations (polygonal style) and colour-graphic capabilities of digital technologies, which testifies to a wide range of approaches to the visualization of advertising ideas.

Practical implications/Original value

Insufficient aesthetics or image level of advertising confirms the need to develop media design – the most promising type of design among others, which is a qualitatively new stage of sociocultural designing of communications. The conceptual foundations of advertising in Ukraine are to expand and deepen the methodology of project thinking, the implementation of the considered scientific methods in practice.

Conclusion

Researching advertising graphics in a wider context, paying special attention to art-aesthetics problems of advertising activity as a form of sociocultural communications, we come to conclusion that the use of artistic means in advertising should be stipulated by orientation to target audience while taking into consideration definite aesthetic ideals and cultural traditions. Advertising products for the mass consumers also must have aesthetic levels and implement education functions. The prospects for the study are to further deepen the proposed provisions, which may serve as a basis for the development of advertising design theory in Ukraine.

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